

**SOCIAL MEDIA: IT'S IMPACT TOWARDS ENGLISH LEARNING
SKILLS OF GRADE 12 STUDENTS AT SULU COLLEGE OF
TECHNOLOGY INCORPORATED**

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Social Media: It's Impact towards English Learning Skills of Grade 12 Students at Sulu College of Technology Incorporated

Leamor J. Panduga,* Nelson U Julhamid
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This is a descriptive-correlational study which determined the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills among the Grade 12 students at Sulu College of Technology, Incorporated during the School Year 2023-2024. After using purposive sampling to obtain 100 samples using the non-probability sampling approach, and utilizing the weighted mean, standard deviation, t-test for independent samples, One-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r, this study reveals the following findings: 1) Out of 100 student-respondents, mostly are female, within the range of 17 years old & below, whose parents mostly have high school level of education, and whose parents' monthly earning pegged at 10,000 & below; 2) Grade 12 students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. generally use social media platforms to a high degree in order to improve their language learning abilities; 3) Generally, Grade 12 senior high school students' assessments of the use of social media platforms towards language learning skills among Grade 12 students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc. did not significantly depend on factors such as gender, age, parent's educational attainment, or parent's average monthly income; 4) Generally, group of Grade 12 senior high school students who perceived the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills in terms of Access to sources of advanced information as Agree is most likely the same group of senior high school students who perceived inspiring and engaging students, motivating and involving students, promoting 21st century skills, pedagogy of education process, attitude towards social media, and cause to personal problems as disagree, respectively; and 5) This study seems to support Connectivism Learning Theory by George Siemens (2004) and Stephen Downes (2005) which espouses that learning is more than our own internal construction of knowledge; thus, what we can reach in our external networks is also considered to be learning. Learning happens when students combine different points of view to make connections between new information and what they already know (Saqr et al., 2018). wherein it happens when peers connect and cooperatively exchange ideas, thoughts, and viewpoints. Connectivism facilitates the justification of collective behaviors among individuals, hence expediting the spread of information across diverse societies.

Keywords: *social media, English learning skills, grade 12 students*

Introduction

Social media is now considered essential for the general public. Social media handles nearly every online task we need to complete. Social media can be an informational resource, source of all information, knowledge, and even human livelihoods. Social media platforms are beginning to offer jobs, online shopping, access to education, and other services more and more.

We can interact socially and communicate with the public through social media. Social media's strength lies in its ability to freely converse and exchange knowledge with a large number of people at once or with every person on the earth.

In October 2023, there will be 4.95 billion social media users worldwide, or 61.4 percent of the world's population. The number of people using social media has increased during the last 12 months as well; since this time last year, 215 million new people have joined the platform. This corresponds to a 4.5 percent annualized growth rate, or 6.8 new users every second on average. based on the most recent data on social media users published by the website DataReportal.

72.5 percent of the total population of the Philippines has a social media account. 30.6 percent of total users aged 18-24 years old. Based on the age range, most of these users belonged to junior high and senior high school students.

It seems hard to live a life nowadays without using social media. Students currently use social media platforms for a variety of purposes. Users of social media can exchange private information, send and receive messages, stay in touch with friends no matter how far away they live, join groups, exchange bookmarks, images, and videos, do business, and learn new things. (In Alaslani and Elandejani, 2020, Hinduja and Patcha, 2008)

Students' usage of social media has escalated to an extreme degree, which has negatively impacted their study time, caused them to use incorrect language and spelling when interacting on social media, and distracted them from their academics (Ndaku, 2013). Students' Grade Point Average (GPA) has suffered as a result of spending a large portion of their study time on social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, and many more.

There are ideas about how social media might improve education. It is indisputable that the internet serves as a social and entertainment platform. Nonetheless, because the internet's role in information distribution is seen favorably, it has a significant impact on academic research. The entire spectrum of resources and information is archived on the internet. Therefore, by looking for the needed content online, a student can improve his or her learning needs. The current study's goal is to find out how social media may be used as a

learning tool to help English language learners become proficient.

Methodology

The research was carried out in one of the private institutions in the Municipality Jolo province of Sulu, Barangay Alat A Chinese School formerly known as Tongjin, and founded by Engr. Sambas I. Hassan Al-Haj, Sulu College Of Technology Incorporated. A descriptive research design method was employed to assess the Impact of social media towards English Learning Skills of Grade 12 Students of Sulu College of Technology Incorporated in this investigation, a purposive sample process was used as a none-probability sampling method. This is because of the senior high school representative sample's availability, accessibility, and time constraints. Student were purposively chosen as subject of the study. It was composed of one-hundred (100) participants and it was selected purposively from the total population of Senior high school students from the aforementioned school, municipality of Jolo, province of Sulu. The research tool utilized in this investigation was modified and derived from a standardized questionnaire which have been employed in previous studies, specifically by Baniyassen (2020). To ensure its suitability for the local context, two panel of experts comprised of faculty members from Sulu State College's School of Graduate Studies were asked to assess the questionnaires. Descriptive and inferential statistics like Frequency counts and percentages, mean and standard deviation, One-way Analysis of variance (ANOVA), The data were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, also known as Pearson's r .

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile

Table 1 provide the results of the demographic profile of the respondents. The survey shows that 29 (29.0%) are male and 71 (71.0%) are female. 44 (44.0%) are within 17 years old & below of age bracket, 49 (49.0%) are within 18-19 years old, and 7 (7.0%) are within 20 years old & above. For the Parents educational attainment, 28 (28.0%) students whose parents with elementary school level of education. While 38 (38.0%) whose parents with high school level of education. There are 28 (28.0%) students whose parents with college level/bachelor's degree. While only 6 (6.0%) whose parents with post-graduate or master's/doctorate degree. 65 (65.0%) of student-respondents are whose parents' monthly income benchmarked at 10,000 & below. While 21 (21.0%) whose parents within 10,001–20,000 bracket. There are 5 (5.00%) students whose parents within 20,001–30,000 and 9 (9.0%) students whose parents' income within 30,001 & above.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile*

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Gender		
Male	29	29.0%
Female	71	71.0%
Age		
17 years old & below	44	44.0%
18-19 years old	49	49.0%
20 years old & above	7	7.0%
Parent's Educational Attainment		
Elementary	28	28.0%
High School	38	38.0%
College	28	28.0%
Master's/Doctorate degree	6	6.0%
Parent's Average Monthly Income		
10,000 & below	65	65.0%
10,001 to 20,000	21	21.0%
20,001 to 30,000	5	5.0%
30,001 & above	9	9.0%

Impact of social media platforms towards language learning skills

Table 2 shows the degree to which social media sites affect language acquisition abilities on access to sources of advanced information under this category, the overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment is 2.9320 with a standard deviation of .60983, meaning that it is classified as Agree or with High Extent. Regarding motivating and involving students. The overall weighted mean score of 3.1000 with a standard deviation of .63960 for the students' assessment falls under this category, where it is evaluated as Agree or with High Extent. In terms of inspiring and enlisting pupils. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment is 3.0057 with a standard deviation of .63691, meaning that it is classified as Agree or with High Extent. Regarding the encouragement of 21st century talents. With a weighted mean score of 3.1200 overall and a standard deviation of .63132, the students' assessment is classified as Agree or with High Extent. Students' assessments, which are scored as Agree or with High Extent, have a total weighted mean score of 3.1100 with a standard deviation of .66211 in terms of pedagogy of the educational process. The students' assessment, which is scored as Disagree or with Low Extent, has a total weighted mean score of 2.4225 with a standard deviation of .56149 about the cause of personal problems. Regarding perspectives on social media. The overall weighted mean score of the students' assessment is 3.2250, with a

standard deviation of .86274, meaning that it is classified as Agree or with High Extent.

Table 2. Impact of Social Media towards English Learning Skills

<i>Areas</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Access to Sources of Advanced Information	2.9320	Agree
Inspiring and Engaging Students	3.1000	Agree
Motivating and Involving Students	3.0057	Agree
Promoting 21st Century Skills	3.1200	Agree
Pedagogy of Education Process	3.1100	Agree
Cause to Personal Problem	2.4225	Disagree
Attitudes towards Social Media	3.2250	Agree

Significant difference in the used of social media platforms towards language learning skills

The general hypothesis, which reads, "When data are classified according to their demographic profile in terms of gender, age, parents' educational attainments, and parents' average monthly income, there is no significant difference in the used of social media platforms towards language learning skills among Grade 12 students," is accepted.

Significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills

These findings show how senior high school students viewed the function of social media sites towards language learning skills in terms of Access to sources of advanced information as Agree is most likely the same set of learners from senior high school who perceived inspiring and engaging students, motivating and involving students, promoting 21st century skills, pedagogy of education process, attitude towards social media, and cause to personal problems as disagree, respectively. In the meantime, it is reasonable to state that, typically, the scope of subcategories included in the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills in terms of access to sources of advanced information, inspiring and engaging students, motivating and involving students, promoting 21st century skills, pedagogy of education process, cause to personal problems, and attitude towards social media is very highly correlated.

Impact of social media platforms towards language learning skills

The following items were rated as Agree or to a high extent by student responders, according to the results: Access to Sources of Advanced Information, Inspiring and Engaging Students, Motivating and Involving Students, Promoting 21st Century Skills, Pedagogy of Education Process, Cause to Personal Problem, and Attitudes towards Social Media.

This finding suggests that the study's student responses agree that there is high extent of the impact of social media platforms the way learners in their senior year of high school immediately receive and imparts information, facilitating critical thinking to the among senior high school students, enhancing students' stimulus or motivation, develop students' motive for deeper thinking and improve team working chances, promoting 21st century skills, enhancing and developing opportunities for social learning to the senior high school students, enhancing the chance of cooperative education, improving self-paced education and learning from and/ with others, and impact of social media platforms and they implore positive attitude towards social media platforms.

The survey also showed that students who participated in the study disagreed about the negative effects that social media platforms had on students' mental and physical health. Students who answered in this area specifically ranked the following things as Low or Disagree: "Causes social difficulties," "Increases alienation," and "Causes loneliness." Numerous studies highlight the detrimental effects of kids' and teens' increased usage of social media, including eating disorders, poor sleep, low self-esteem, anxiety, and sadness, as well as unprofessional behavior (Anne Casey Foundation, 2023).

Advanced information sources such as the net, print papers, diaries, TV or radio transcripts, pamphlets, photos, and other artifacts are invaluable. They assist us in determining the veracity of the information we obtain. Since not all sources are trustworthy and accurate, being aware of them is crucial while acquiring information or data. It also serves to provide us with reliable proof. [Brainly.ph, 2021].

Significant difference in the used of social media platforms towards language learning skills

This survey indicates that among students in Grade 12, the mean differences across all subcategories related to the use of social media platforms for language learning are not statistically significant at alpha.05. This indicates that there is no difference in the opinions of male and female student responders about the usage of social media platforms for language learning among students in Grade 12. According to this research, a male student may not always have an advantage over a female student when it comes to observing how social media platforms are utilized by Grade 12 students to improve their language learning abilities, or vice versa.

Student-respondents vary in age range, parents' educational attainment and parents average monthly income yet they do not differ in their perceptions in the direction of the used of social media platforms towards language learning skills among Grade12 students. The hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the used of social media platforms towards language learning skills among Grade12 students when information is classified according to their demographic profile in terms of age, parents educational attainment and parent's average monthly income" is accepted.

Significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills

Generally, the extent of sub-categories subsumed under the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills in terms of access to sources of advanced information, inspiring and engaging students, motivating and involving students, promoting 21st century skills, pedagogy of education process, cause to personal problems, and attitude towards social media is very highly correlated.

Thus, the hypothesis that "No significant correlation exists between the sub-categories that fall under the role of social media platforms' role in language learning skills" among the Grade 12 students at Sulu College of Technology, Incorporated" is rejected.

The research conducted by shepherd (2024) showed that on Facebook, the greatest demography on the platform is represented by those between the ages of 25 and 34. On Instagram, that age group ranks second, with 18 to 24 years old taking the top spot in terms of usage. Additionally, 37% of Twitter users are female, indicating a predominance of male users.

Social media can be used as a powerful tool to learn and practice a language. Learners can use platforms to connect with native speakers and practice their language skills. They can also find useful resources to help them improve their language learning.

Conclusion

The conclusions drawn from this study's findings are as follows: Grade 12 senior high school students involved in this study are suitably represented in terms of age, gender and parents' educational attainment, and parents average monthly income. There is typically a significant degree on the use of social media platforms towards language learning skills among Grade12 students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Generally, variables gender, age, level of education of parents, and parents average monthly income do not significantly mediate in ways how Grade 12 senior high school students assessed the use of social media platforms towards language learning skills among Grade12 students at Sulu College of Technology, Inc.

Generally, group of Grade 12 senior high school students who perceived the role of social media platforms towards language learning skills in terms of Access to sources of advanced information as Agree is most likely the identical group of senior high school students who perceived inspiring and engaging students, motivating and involving students, promoting 21st century skills, pedagogy of education process, attitude towards social media, and cause to personal problems as disagree, respectively.

This study appears to confirm George Siemens' (2004) and Stephen Downes' (2005) Connectivism Learning Theory, which maintains that learning is more than just our internal creation of knowledge and that learning also includes what we can access through external networks. Learning happens when peers connect and share thoughts, viewpoints, and ideas through a collaborative process. This process involves synthesizing diverse viewpoints and helps learners link disparate knowledge to enhance what they already know (Saqr et al., 2018). Connectivism makes it possible for a group of individuals to justify their actions, which speeds up the dissemination of information across.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Leamor Jali Panduga, LPT

Sulu State College - Philippines

Nelson U. Julhamid, PhD

Sulu State College - Philippines